

Soil Grain Size analysis

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Abstract

Grain size analysis is conducted to determine the particle grain size present in a soil sample. The grain analysis is expressed as a percentage of the total dry weight. The most commonly used methods include sieve analysis and hydrometer analysis. This report presents a particle size analysis to determine the percentage of grain sizes in a soil sample in accordance with the ASTM standards. The experiment report concludes a sample analysis uniformly distributed after being passed through Unified soil grading criteria. The experiment errors are assumed to be negligible due to the small discrepancy in the two test results. The report objectives include acquiring the distribution of soil particles in the sample and producing data with errors less than the acceptable 2% and generating a semi-logarithmic plot. The semi-logarithmic plot displays the distribution of particle sizes of the soil and identifies the soil grading with the use of the graph data points.

Introduction

Screening is defined as the separation of particle mixtures into two or more fractions through a screening surface. There exist a number of methods of determining of size distribution, one of which is the sieve analysis. Sieve analysis is also one of the best and oldest size distribution determination methods. Mass and volume are used in the definition of distribution of particle sizes. In light of this, the distribution of particulate material is divided into fractions and their weights determined to ease the analysis of the relatively broad particle size spectrum. This also increases the speed and reliability of the analysis (Boerner and Elaine 45). The soil sample

is subjected to vertical and horizontal movements to bring about relative particle and sieve movement. The sample is then passed through a sieve mesh and the finer grains get through while the coarse ones are retained on the surface of the sieve. The ratio of the size of the particle to the openings of the sieve determines the ability of the particles getting through the sieve. Other factors include the particle orientation and the number of times the particles encounter the mesh openings.

This laboratory report presents the result and an analysis of a test performed to determine the percentage of finer grained sizes of grains performed within a soil. The size analysis is used to determine the particle distribution of the coarser and larger sized particles. The distribution of different sizes of grains affects soil engineering properties. The analysis of sizes of grains gives the grain size distribution necessary for soil classification (Boerner and Elaine 46).

Methodology

The analysis of the report followed the standard test procedures for sieve analysis and the Atterberg limit test procedures. The equipment needed for the experiment and analysis of the soil samples include a balance, cleaning brush, sieve shaker and set of sieves. The sieve weights and the bottom pan were taken. The dry soil samples were also taken. The sieves were cleaned and assembled in an ascending order of sieve numbers with sieve #200 at the bottom. The pan was placed below the bottom sieve and soil sample carefully poured into the top sieve and cap placed over it. The sieve stack was then shaken using a mechanical shaker after which it was removed and weights of each sieve carefully taken and recorded.

Analysis of data

Sieve analysis

The mass of the retained soil was obtained by subtraction the empty sieve weight from the sieve mass of the sieve plus the soil retained. The mass was recorded on the data sheet. The sums of the retained masses were expected to approximately be equal to the initial soil sample mass and more than 2 percentage loss is unsatisfactory.

The percentage mass of retained soil is calculated by dividing weight retained by each sieve by the original mass of the sample.

The percent finer, also referred to as the percent passing, is calculated by subtracting the retained percentage from 100.

Computation of C_c and C_u for the soil sample- Brown and tan gravelling sand

Sieve no	Sieve opening	Mass of soil retained on each sieve(g)	Percentage of mass retained on each sieve, R_n	Cumulative percentage retained yR_n	Percentage finer $100-Y, R_n$
1''	25 mm	464.03-T=57.14	12.3	12.3	87.7
¾''	19 mm	498.06-T=34.03	6.8	19.1	80.9
3/8''	9.5 mm	569.53-T=71.47	12.5	31.6	68.4
4	4.75 mm	679.18-T=109.65	16.1	47.7	52.3
10	2 mm	829.56-T=150.38	18.1	65.8	34.2
20	850 mm	950.00-T=120.44	12.7	78.5	21.5
40	425 mm	1009.00-T=59	5.8	84.3	15.7
100	150 mm	1019.96-T=10	0.01	84.31	15.69

200	75 mm	0.01			
Pan		0.01			

Discussion

More than 35% passes through the no 200 sieve means the soil sample was clay. This means that the soil could be a-4, A-5, A-6 or A-7. The liquid limit is 48 while the plasticity index is 28. The liquid limit is less than 40 and the Plasticity index is greater than eleven. This means that the soil sample could fall in the A-6 group.

$$GI = (F_{200} - 35) [0.02 + 0.005(LL - 40)] + 0.01(F_{200} - 15)(PI - 10)$$

$$GI = (41 - 35)[0.02 + 0.005(31 - 40)] + 0.01(41 - 15)(12 - 10)$$

$$= 0.37 \sim 0$$

This means that the soil is A-6.

Graph: percentage finer against particle sizes

The Atterberg limit test

The procedure is aimed at determining the plastic and liquid limits of the fine grained of soil. The water content of a soil sample is known as its plastic limit in form of percentage. At this limit, the soil can no be deformed any more by rolling into a 3.2mm (1.8 in.) diameter threads without crumbling. The procedure observes the standards of the ASTM for liquid limit, plastic limit and soil plasticity index.

Albert Atterberg, a Swedish soil scientist, first came up with the definition of seven consistency limits and classified the fine grained soils. In the present day engineering practice, only two of the limits are mostly used, namely, the plastic limits and the liquid limits. The shrinkage limit is also used in the current practice. These limits are based on soil moisture content. The plastic limit refers to the content of moisture defining the soil changes to the flexible plastic state from the semi-solid state. Many soil engineering properties are related to the plastic limits and the liquid limit. These limits are also used in the classification of fine-grained soil in accordance with the AASHTO or Unified Soil Classification System

Methodology

The plastic limit

Weights and numbers of empty moisture cans with lids are recorded on the data sheet. The equipment necessary for a successful experiment include a porcelain evaporating dish, wash bottle with distilled water, a drying oven set at 105 degrees centigrade, moisture cans and a glass plate. Distilled water is added to the remaining quarter of the soil until it reaches a consistency. A consistency is the point when the soil sample can be rolled without it sticking to hands. The soil is then formed into ellipsoidal mass and rolled between the palms and a glass plate using

enough pressure into a uniform diameter thread by stroking it 90 times a minute. The thread is then deformed until the diameter reaches around 3.2mm (1.8 in.) for around two minutes.

When a correct diameter is reached, the thread is broken into several pieces and each piece kneaded and reformed into ellipsoidal masses and then re-rolled. This procedure continues while gathering, kneading and re-rolling the threads until they crumble under the required pressure until when they cannot be rolled further into a 3.2mm diameter thread. The portions are then gathered and crumbled and the soil placed into moisture can and covered. It is then weighed and its mass recorded. The lid is then removed and the can is placed into an oven and left to stay in it for at least 16 hours. With the measurements herein, the water content is determined.

Computation of C_c and C_u of wet soil- fine well graded sand with small gravel , well rounded

Sieve no	Sieve opening	Mass of soil retained on each sieve(g)	Percentage of mass retained on each sieve, R_n	Cumulative percentage retained yR_n	Percentage finer $100-Y, R_n$
4	4.75mm	52.02	0.07	0.07	99.93
10	2mm	202.39	24.39	24.46	75.54
20	850mm	204.39	21.51	45.97	54.03
40	425mm	37.43	3.7	49.67	50.33
100	150mm	1.0	0.00	49.67	50.33
200	75m	0.1	1000	1049.67	949.67
PAN	Passing	0.02	200	1249.67	1149.67

	200				
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Graph: percentage finer against particle sizes

More than 35% passes through the no 200 sieve meaning that the soil sample was also clay. This means that the soil could be a-4, A-5, A-6 or A-7. The liquid limit is 56 while the plasticity index is 42. The liquid limit is less than 40 and the Plasticity index is greater than eleven. This means that the soil sample could fall in the A-6 group.

$$GI = (F_{200} - 35) [0.02 + 0.005(LL - 40) + 0.01(F_{200} - 15)(PI - 10)]$$

$$GI = (41 - 35)[0.02 + 0.005(31 - 40) + 0.01(41 - 15)(12 - 10)]$$

=0.37 ~ 0

This implies that the soil also falls in the A-6.

Similar tests can be performed using the hydrometer and the standard proctor test methods.

Works cited

Boerner, Ralph EJ, and Elaine Kennedy Sutherland. "Physiography, geology, and soil classification." *Characteristics of mixed oak forest ecosystems in southern Ohio prior to the reintroduction of fire. USDA Forest Service, Northeastern Research Station General Technical Report NE-299, Newtown Square, PA* (2003): 43-46.